

QUANTUM PHASE DETECTION IN THE ANNNI MODEL ON QUANTUM PROCESSOR

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AUTHOR(S):

Saverio Monaco

SUPERVISOR(S):

Oriel Kiss

Michele Grossi

Sofia Vallecorsa

Antonio Mandarino

ABSTRACT

Ising Models are a group of simple mathematical models originally designed to describe the nature of ferromagnetism and, more generally, phase-transitions, or sudden changes in a system's properties. In this work we analyse specifically the Axial Next-Nearest Neighbour Interaction (ANNNI) model that presents three distinct phases, which transition points lack an analytical solution and are often tackled using numerical methods. In order to take advantage of the benefit of working directly with quantum data, we deployed quantum machine learning methods. To be more precise, we prepared the quantum states using the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) algorithm, and for the phase-mapping task, we employed both supervised and unsupervised QML approaches. We specifically highlight the Quantum Convolutional Neural Network (QCNN) and Quantum Autoencoder models.

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1 Introduction

The popularity of quantum computers has grown in recent years due to numerous claims that they are able to outperform classical computers in a variety of computational tasks.

Even though Quantum Computing is still in its infancy, many quantum algorithms are already being created and evaluated, primarily through simulations on classical computing platforms. Among all these new methods, Quantum Machine Learning attracted the most interest being particularly versatile and noise resistant.

In this work, we explore the phase transitions of the Axial Next-Nearest Neighbour Interaction (ANNNI) model, which is a member of the family of the Ising models, using supervised and unsupervised techniques from quantum machine learning. For instance, the examined system is firstly presented, introducing in the meantime the main tools from quantum mechanics needed for the employed algorithms then the QML models are presented.

1.1 The ANNNI Model

Consider a chain of spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles in a transverse magnetic field μ , in which each particle can interact with its neighbouring and its next-neighbouring spins.

Figure 1: Visual representation of an Ising Chain Model

1.1.1 State of the ANNNI model

For any given quantum system, the object that describes the current state of it is called *wavefunction* ($|\psi\rangle$) and it is a vector of a space called *Hilbert Space*.

For a single spin the *Hilbert space* is two-dimensional and its *wavefunction* can be written using the basis $\{|\uparrow\rangle, |\downarrow\rangle\}$, namely a combination of the states $|\uparrow\rangle$ and $|\downarrow\rangle$ (respectively the state of the spin being *up* or *down*):

$$|\psi\rangle = a \cdot |\uparrow\rangle + b \cdot |\downarrow\rangle, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{C}, \quad a^2 + b^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

Generalizing, for a given system of n spins, the *wavefunction* is a vector of a 2^n -dimensional *Hilbert space* expressed using the basis of all possible combinations of \uparrow and \downarrow between each spin:

$$|\psi\rangle = c_1 \cdot |\uparrow\uparrow \dots \uparrow\uparrow\rangle + c_2 \cdot |\uparrow\uparrow \dots \uparrow\downarrow\rangle + \\ + c_3 \cdot |\uparrow\uparrow \dots \downarrow\uparrow\rangle + \dots + c_{2^n} |\downarrow\downarrow \dots \downarrow\downarrow\rangle \quad (2)$$

$$c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{2^n} \in \mathbb{C}, \quad c_1^2 + c_2^2 + \dots + c_{2^n}^2 = 1$$

1.1.2 Hamiltonian of the ANNNI model

Any quantum system is fully described by the operator (represented as a matrix) called Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} .

The Hamiltonian of the studied system is:

$$\mathcal{H} = J_1 \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_x^i \otimes \sigma_x^{i+1} - J_2 \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sigma_x^i \otimes \sigma_x^{i+2} + \mu \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_z^i \quad (3)$$

Where:

- J_1 is the interaction strength between neighbouring spins (coupling constant);
- J_2 is the interaction strength between next-neighbouring spins;
- μ is the intensity of the magnetic field;
- σ_x and σ_z are the Pauli matrices acting on the i -th spin:

$$\sigma_x = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix};$$

Namely the first and second term describe respectively the interactions between the nearest neighbouring and next-nearest neighbouring spins, while the third describes the interaction between each spin and the magnetic field.

By rearranging the terms in the Hamiltonian, we can write it simply as:

$$\mathcal{H} = -J_1 \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_x^i \sigma_x^{i+1} - \kappa \sigma_x^i \sigma_x^{i+2} - h \sigma_z^i \quad (4)$$

Where: $\kappa = J_2/J_1$ and $h = \mu/J_1$.

Given a system \mathcal{H} and a state $|\psi\rangle$, the energy of the state is given by the product:

$$E(|\psi\rangle) = \langle \psi | \mathcal{H} | \psi \rangle \quad (5)$$

Therefore, we refer to the wavefunction that results in the systems lowest possible energy as the *ground-state wavefunction*:

$$\psi_{GS} := \min_{\psi} \langle \psi | \mathcal{H} | \psi \rangle \quad (6)$$

1.1.3 Phase-transitions of the ANNNI model

The phase mapping of the system is rather complex, displaying three distinct quantum phases: ferro-, antiferro-, and para-magnetic. This is due to the interaction between neighboring spins and next-neighboring spins (κ) as well as the presence of the magnetic field (h). The system results integrable, that is it has analytical solutions, just for the trivial cases, namely when either $h = 0$ or $\kappa = 0$ letting our model results in a standard Ising Chain for the former, or in an Ising Chain with next-neighbour interaction and no magnetic field for the latter.

Even though the system cannot be solved analytically, the entire phase diagram has already

Figure 2: Phase diagram of the ANNNI model and the state of the art transition lines between ferro- and para-magnetic h_I and between antiphase and paramagnetic h_C

been investigated using the Renormalization Group and Montecarlo techniques[1], yielding the phase-transition curves shown below:

$$\text{Ferro-Paramagnetic: } h_I(\kappa) = \frac{1 - \kappa}{\kappa} \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{1 - 3\kappa + 4\kappa^2}{1 - \kappa}} \right) \quad \kappa \in [0, .5[\quad (7)$$

$$\text{Anti.-Paramagnetic: } h_C(\kappa) = 1.05\sqrt{(x - 0.5)(x - 0.1)} \quad \kappa \in [0.5, 1] \quad (8)$$

To be precise, the actual phase diagram of the ANNNI model is supposed to be much richer, involving two pseudo-phase transitions: one within the paramagnetic subspace and the other within the antiphase space:

$$\text{Paramagnetic: } h_{PE}(\kappa) = \frac{1}{4\kappa} - \kappa \quad \kappa \in [0, .5[\quad (9)$$

$$\text{Antiphase: } h_{FP}(\kappa) = 1.05(\kappa - 0.5) \quad \kappa \in [0.5, 1] \quad (10)$$

Figure 3: Phase diagram of the ANNNI model and the state of the art transition with the addition to the two pseudo-transition phase lines: the Peshel-Emery line (h_{PE}) and the floating-phase line (h_{FP})

1.1.4 ANNNI model States Encoding

Before even developing any QML model, it is necessary to find the most convenient way to embed the data into the quantum circuits.

For the task of finding the phase of the system, the inputs of the QML models will be the wavefunctions, which will be encoded in the circuit using the most trivial embedding, in which each wire represents a spin. This means that if we need to simulate 6 spins of the ANNNI model, 6 quantum wires will be needed.

This embedding has the utmost importance for the functioning of the Quantum Convolutional Neural Network, in which the local spatial features play a fundamental role.

2 Methods

This section explains the primary quantum algorithms as they are implemented in Python using the specific QML-library *PennyLane*.

2.1 Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)

The *Ground-state wavefunction* (eq. 6) of a given system can be found using the iterative quantum algorithm Variational Quantum Eigensolver, which results will be used as input to train and test the QML models.

Recalling that the *ground-state wavefunction* is the state with the lowest possible energy, and that the energy of a system given the state is

$$E(|\psi\rangle) = \langle\psi|\mathcal{H}|\psi\rangle$$

we can perform an optimization routine in which the output of the VQE is the parametrized wavefunction, which parameters will be optimized such that the *expectation value* of the output with the Hamiltonian \mathcal{H} is minimum[3]:

Figure 4: Optimization routine of the VQE algorithm: 0. Choice of the Ansatz and initialization of the parameters, 1. Get the Output from the parametrized quantum circuit, 2. Compute the Energy given the Hamiltonian, 3. Update the parameter of the circuit using a classical optimizer, Repeat 1,2,3...

Image modified from the [1QBit OpenQEMIST documentation](#)

Arguably, the most critical part of this algorithm, is the choice of the *Ansatz*, namely the structure of the quantum circuit to train.

To pick the best *Ansatz* it is necessary to consider:

- the eventual limitation of the hardware;
- the physical insights of the model;
- the expressive capabilities.

After numerous tests, the chosen *Ansatz* consists in multiple repetitions of the same circuit block:

Figure 5: Single block of the VQE circuit inspired from paper "Expressibility and Entangling Capability of Parameterized Quantum Circuits for Hybrid Quantum-Classical Algorithms"[5]

For instance it consists in a layer of *Hadamard-gates*, a layer of *CNOT-gates* to establish entanglement between neighbouring wires/spins and a final layer of independent R_Y rotations; since the only parametrized gates are the R_Y rotations, the number of total parameters needed per repetition of the VQE block is equal to the number of wires, hence the final number of parameters N_{params} amounts to:

$$N_{params} = L \cdot N \quad (11)$$

where N is the number of wires/spins and L is the number of repetition of the circuit-block.

It was observed that the more repetitions of the VQE-block led to a higher accuracy of the output *Ground-state wavefunctions*, a deeper architecture may be then more accurate, but its actual implementation on quantum hardware will be more prone to decoherence errors.

Once approximated the *ground-state wavefunctions* for many combinations of (κ, h) , each VQE circuit can be used as input for training the classifiers. Being each output $|\psi(\theta, \kappa, h)\rangle$ a quantum state, it cannot be measured, otherwise it will lose its superposition collapsing in a single *eigen-state* of the system. The solution is to *prepend* VQE-circuits one by one when training the classifier, updating only the parameters related to the latter.

Algorithm of the VQE:

1. Choose the Ansatz
2. Set the initial parameters $\vec{\theta}_0$
3. Iterate:
 - 3.1. Get $|\psi(\theta, \kappa, h)\rangle$ from the circuit
 - 3.2. Compute $E(\theta, \kappa, h) = \langle \psi(\theta, \kappa, h) | \mathcal{H} | \psi(\theta, \kappa, h) \rangle$
 - 3.3. Compute and update the new parameters of the circuit: $\vec{\theta} \rightarrow \vec{\theta}'$

Figure 6: Scheme of training of classifier model given the VQE inputs

2.2 Quantum Convolutional Neural Network (QCNN)

The first phase-mapping model is the QCNN, its architecture is inspired by the classical counterpart (CNNs) which are employed where spatial information is supposed to be critical in the learning task i.e. image processing; as a matter of fact the information concerning the entanglement between neighboring spins may actually be crucial for the process of identifying phases in the ANNNI model, additionally QCNNs have been shown to be resistant to *barren plateau*[4] which is the quantum equivalent of the *gradient vanishing problem* in classical machine learning. Just as CNNs, the architecture is made up of convolution and pooling layers; the former consists in layers of R_Y rotations and CNOTs as in figure 7a, the latter instead reduces the number of wires by measuring half of the current active ones, and based on the result of each measurement, it applies a different rotation to the next wire as in figure 7b.

(a) Example structure for the Convolution block for $N = 6$

(b) Example structure for the Convolution block with $N = 6$

The complete architecture of the QCNN consists in repetitions of Convolution-block + Pooling-block until only two wires are active, hence, the total number of parameters of the circuit depends on the amount of initial wires/spins.

The input is $|0\rangle^{\otimes N}$, which is then passed through a VQE-circuit($\vec{\theta}$) to obtain $\psi(\vec{\theta})$ that is

Figure 8: Complete architecture of the QCNN

the actual training-input of the classifier. The output instead is the probability vector of the two-state system remained:

$$\text{Output: } [p_0 \equiv \mathbb{P}(|00\rangle), p_1 \equiv \mathbb{P}(|01\rangle), p_2 \equiv \mathbb{P}(|10\rangle), p_3 \equiv \mathbb{P}(|11\rangle)] \quad (12)$$

The ANNNI model comprises three phases: Antiphase, Paramagnetic, and Ferromagnetic, hence it is possible to associate each phase with a single eigenstate of a two-wires system:

$$\text{Paramagnetic} \leftrightarrow |11\rangle; \quad \text{Antiphase} \leftrightarrow |10\rangle$$

$$\text{Ferromagnetic} \leftrightarrow |01\rangle; \quad \text{Trash case} \leftrightarrow |00\rangle$$

Thereby, during training the parameters of the classifier will be tweaked such that when the input of the model is a given phase, the probability of its relative two-wires state will be much higher than all the other 3. Notice the output vector is 4-dimensional, while only 3 dimensions were needed.

The classifier is trained through classical optimization, minimizing the multi-class cross entropy \mathcal{L} :

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}|} \sum_{(\kappa, h) \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{j=1}^K y_j(\kappa, h) \log(p_j(\kappa, h)) \quad (13)$$

where \mathcal{S} is the Training Set, y_j and p_j are respectively the j -th label and its model prediction.

As mentioned in 1.1.3 at page 4, the model is not solvable for the non-trivial cases (namely when h or κ are zero), this means that we only have access to the labels of a overly restricted $h - \kappa$ space.

Algorithm of the QCNN:

1. Set the initial parameters $\vec{\omega}_0$
2. Iterate for epoch in tot_epochs:
 - 2.1. Iterate for $j \in \mathcal{S}$:
 - 2.1.1 Link the j -th trained VQE to the QCNN
 - 2.1.2 Get p_j , the prediction of the model for the j -th input
 - 2.2 Compute the loss \mathcal{L}
 - 2.3 Update the parameter vector $\vec{\omega} \rightarrow \vec{\omega}'$

2.3 Quantum Autoencoder

The Quantum Autoencoder/Anomaly Detector is an *unsupervised quantum machine learning* circuit inspired by classical Encoders.

The model uses a trained VQE circuit as input (and as a result, the system's ground-state wavefunction) and modifies its parameters so that the output state can be expressed as the tensor product:

$$\psi(\kappa, h, \vec{\theta}) \longrightarrow \phi \otimes |0\rangle^{\otimes K} \quad (14)$$

that is, the final state is the tensor product of $|0\rangle$ repeated K times, which is a state with no useful information and a compressed ψ state represented by $N - K$ wires containing most information from the initial state.

Figure 9: Scheme of the Anomaly detection circuit for $N = 6$

The training is performed such that the K wires in the middle of the circuit (fig 9) get to the $|0\rangle$ state, these wires are called *trash qubits*.

The loss of such task is:

$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j \in q_T} (1 - \langle Z_j \rangle) \quad (15)$$

$\langle Z_i \rangle$ is the expectation value in the Z -basis of the i -th qubit, if the qubit is measured as $|0\rangle$, Z_i is 1, conversely if the qubit is measured as $|1\rangle$, Z_i is -1. It is then obvious that the parameters are tweaked such that the measurement of the trash qubits are mostly on the $|0\rangle$ state individually, resulting in the state output at equation 14.

The circuit *Ansatz* is inspired from the paper [2], it consists in a layer of individual R_Y and R_Z rotations for each wire, in addition to entanglement layers between a non-trash qubit and a trash-qubit and among trash-qubits.

Being an unsupervised quantum machine learning model it does not suffer from the non-integrability of the system since labels are not needed, hence we can use any state for training, not only the trivial ones.

Algorithm of the Quantum Anomaly Detector:

1. Set the initial parameters $\vec{\beta}_0$ for the Anomaly Detector and choose a single input state $\psi(\kappa, h, \vec{\theta})$
2. Iterate for epoch in tot_epochs:
 - 2.1 Measure the trash qubits in the Z -basis, obtaining $\langle Z_j \rangle$
 - 2.2 Compute the loss \mathcal{C}
 - 2.3 Update the parameter vector $\vec{\beta} \rightarrow \vec{\beta}'$

3 Results

3.1 VQE

The ranges of the system parameters κ and h , are 0 to 1 and 0 to 2, respectively. The state-space was discretized for both systems with 6 and 12 spins so that each parameter can have 100 different values, giving the VQE method a total of 20,000 states to train on.

The enormous number of different states to obtain through VQE would have made the task impossible without any optimization, however in addition to parallelization and basic computational optimization, the implementation of *parameters recycling* reduced significantly the execution times, in which the trained parameters of one state were used as initial parameters of the adjacent ones.

During training, the accuracy of the states considered is the relative energy error with the true states computed by diagonalization of the hamiltonian matrices:

$$\text{Accuracy}^{(i)} = \left| \frac{E_{true}^{(i)} - E_{VQE}^{(i)}}{E_{true}^{(i)}} \right| \quad (16)$$

in which we required each relative error to be below 0.01. In order to achieve this high accuracy, the 12 spins system required a deeper architecture with 9 repetitions of the VQE block (fig. 5), while the 6 spins system required only 6.

Figure 10: Energy accuracies of the VQE states for 8 spins and 12 spins

The relative energy errors of the VQE states are depicted in the figures above; each point has an error below the required threshold.

It was observed that the states close to transitions are more difficult to replicate through VQE for both the 6 and 12 spins systems, this is in all likelihood due to their unique configuration of spins.

3.2 QCNN

Once obtained the VQE circuit of all the possible parameters combinations, the classification via QCNN was successfully implemented for both 6 and 12 spins cases:

Figure 11: Visualization of the classification of the QCNN for (b) 8 spins and (e) 12 spins

The figure above is a visualization of the classification of the QCNN in which the Blue-Green-Yellow channels are used to represent the probabilities of the state being ferromagnetic, paramagnetic and antiphase respectively.

It was soon assumed that not every point on the training set is required to achieve high accuracy, thus it was explored what may be the smallest size of a training-set before saturation of the performance. For each investigated size of the subset, 100 QCNNs were trained drawing the input *groundstates* randomly, finally the accuracies and standard deviation were estimated:

Figure 12: Accuracy of the QCNN for limited random training points for (a) 6 spins and (d) 12 spins.

As the two figures above suggest, the QCNN does not require a large amount of datapoints to perform an accurate classification, for ~ 10 datapoints the accuracy of the QCNN already plateaus and no more training data will significantly improve its performance.

3.3 Quantum Autoencoder

Lastly, the Anomaly Detector was successfully implemented. By training the model on a single ground-state wavefunction, the encoder is capable to compress states that are similar to the one it was trained with, namely the states with the same phase, while it will perform poorly on states that have different phases.

Figure 13: Encoding score of the Anomaly Detector for (c) 8 spins and (f) 12 spins trained on the (0,0) point of the parameter space

In the two figures above, the encoding scores are depicted for the Anomaly Detectors trained on the (0,0) point of the parameter space. As expected the trained models were capable to compress the ferromagnetic states accordingly while the paramagnetic and antiphase points were not. Additionally the two other states were compressed with different scores in a consistent manner leading the encoding scores differences follow qualitatively the true transition lines.

4 Conclusions

All three algorithms were successfully simulated on a classical computer. In order to produce an accurate model, the Ansatz selection turned out to be the most critical step. Finding the best circuits took the most time due to the vast number of possible configurations; fortunately, the computation was moved early in the project to the GPU, which reduced the amount of time needed by orders of magnitude.

The project can be expanded by including noise in the circuits to more accurately simulate current quantum hardware because qubits cannot fully maintain coherence due to the noisy environment. Additionally by restricting the gate types and overall gate count, the Ansatz can also be constrained to resemble current quantum circuits.

Further work on this project can consist in finding the other two lines showed in figure 3 at page 5. These pseudo-transitions involve the behaviour of multiple spins arranging themselves in pairs and triples. It is supposed that in order to detect these behaviours, more spins are needed to be simulated; however, the limited memory and simulation times on classical hardware are the current two main restrictions.

5 References

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6 Appendix

6.1 Code specifications

The package code was built in *Python*, using the *Pennylane* library by *Xanadu* for simulating quantum circuits on classical hardware and *JAX* by *Google* as the backend to bring parallelized computations on GPU, reducing the simulation times significantly.

The source code of the project can be found on the [CERN-IT-INNOVATION Github page](#). In `src/PhaseEstimation` all the functions and classes of the package *PhaseEstimation* can be found:

- `general.py`: module for generic functions for other modules;
- `losses.py`: implements loss functions and regularizers for VQE, QCNN and Encoder;
- `circuits.py`: implements base circuit layouts for all the models used;
- `annni_model.py`: implements functions for treating the Hamiltonian class;
- `hamiltonians.py`: implements the base class for spin-models Hamiltonians;
- `vqe.py`: implements the VQE class for the ANNNI model;
- `qcnm.py`: implements the QCNN class;
- `encoder.py`: implements the Anomaly Detection class;
- `visualization.py`: implements visualization functions.

Additionally, several tutorials of the main algorithms can be found in `notebooks/` as `.ipynb` files.

